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Modulation of Tau Phosphorylation by Oxidative Stress: Insights into the Interplay among LKB1, AMPK, and Akt Pathways in Differentiated SH-SY5Y Cells

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Abstract

Background: Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the accumulation of hyperphosphorylated tau (p-tau) in neurofibrillary tangles and beta-amyloid plaques. The role of oxidative stress (OS) in AD progression remains unclear.

Methods: Using SH-SY5Y human neuroblastoma cells as an in vitro model, we investigated the impact of OS on tau phosphorylation. Mature neurons were exposed to varying concentrations of hydrogen peroxide for different durations (1-5 days) to simulate OS. Western blot analysis was employed to quantify key signalling pathways (LKB1, AMPK, and Akt) and antioxidant enzymes (SOD2, p1, p4, and catalase).

Results: Prolonged OS exposure resulted in tau hyperphosphorylation at Ser262, a tau residue sensitive to AMPK, despite initial dephosphorylation. Treatment with compound C (CC), an AMPK inhibitor, prevented this effect. OS activated LKB1 and AMPK, enhanced by CC and rapamycin, while CC and rapamycin suppressed OS-induced Akt activity. SOD2, the primary defence against OS, increased, whereas p1 and catalase, the secondary defence, decreased. P4 activity remained unchanged. Notably, CC consistently reduced antioxidant enzyme activity across experimental groups.

Conclusion: OS activates the LKB1, AMPK, and Akt signalling pathways. The interplay between LKB1's stimulatory effect and Akt's inhibitory effect on AMPK leads to AMPK activation and subsequent tau hyperphosphorylation. AMPK facilitates the protective response mediated by SOD2 against OS, but prolonged OS exposure induces tau hyperphosphorylation. Therefore, OS likely serves as a trigger for AD pathology.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease, Oxidative stress (OS), Tau phosphorylation, LKB1/AMPK pathway, Akt pathway, Superoxide dismutase (SOD2), Peroxiredoxin (p), Catalase

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a significant global health issue, ranking as the third leading cause of death worldwide. It is characterized by a progressive decline in cognitive function and memory. The key pathological features of AD encompass the formation of extracellular beta-amyloid (A β) aggregates, neurofibrillary tangles

(NFTs) composed of hyperphosphorylated tau (p-tau), and substantial neuronal loss[1-3].

The identification of A β as the primary constituent of senile plaques by Glenner and Wong [4] has propelled the A β cascade hypothesis to the forefront of AD research. This hypothesis posits that A β deposition serves as the initial trigger in the pathogenesis of AD,

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subsequently giving rise to the development of other hallmarks associated with the disease [5-7]. Supporting evidence for this notion has emerged through studies demonstrating the presence of amyloid precursor protein (APP) gene mutations on chromosome 21 in many cases of familial AD [8]. However, challenges to the beta-amyloid hypothesis have surfaced through reports documenting the existence of senile plaques in cognitively normal individuals who do not exhibit clinical symptoms of AD [9]. Conversely, alternative studies have proposed that hyperphosphorylated tau (p-tau) within neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) serves as the upstream initiator of Alzheimer's disease (AD) events [10].

The presence of NFTs in AD subjects exhibiting pronounced neurodegeneration and impaired memory, coupled with the strong correlation between NFTs and p-tau levels in the cerebrospinal fluid of affected individuals, has provided substantial support for this hypothesis [11; 12]. Nevertheless, this hypothesis has faced challenges due to the distinct spatial and temporal distribution patterns observed in the deposition of A β plaques, NFTs, and significant neuronal loss in brain regions where NFTs are absent [13]. These findings have raised critical questions regarding the role of hyperphosphorylated tau as the primary trigger for AD pathology, thereby prompting researchers to explore alternative possibilities [14-16].

While the precise trigger responsible for initiating the cascade of Alzheimer's disease (AD) events remains to be fully elucidated, one indisputable fact is the prominent role played by aging as the primary risk factor associated with AD development [17]. As individuals age, their cells become increasingly susceptible to oxidative stress (OS) due to the presence of reactive oxygen species (ROS) as metabolic by-products [18; 19]. ROS have the potential to

disrupt the activity of enzymes, receptors, and transporters by influencing transcriptional processes and directly impacting proteins and lipids.

In individuals with healthy physiology, intracellular antioxidants such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, and peroxiredoxins (p) work diligently to tightly regulate ROS levels and counteract their detrimental effects [18; 19]. However, prolonged exposure to ROS over time can lead to mitochondrial dysfunction, impairing the functionality of these scavenging systems and resulting in heightened levels of ROS and subsequent cellular damage [18]. Although the precise mechanism linking ROS to AD pathology has yet to be fully comprehended, it is postulated that ROS may influence cellular metabolic pathways and serve as mediators of AD events.

Adenosine monophosphate protein kinase (AMPK), a pivotal metabolic regulator within cells, plays a critical role in maintaining energy homeostasis through its involvement in glucose and lipid metabolism. Intriguingly, AMPK also exhibits tau kinase activity under various conditions [20; 21]. The phosphorylation and activation of AMPK are modulated by liver kinase B1 (LKB1) in response to stress stimuli, independent of changes in ATP levels [22; 23]. Notably, oxidative stress (OS) represents one example of a stress condition that exerts an influence on AMPK activation by interacting with its upstream kinases, including LKB1 and Akt [23; 24]. Consequently, the interplay between LKB1, AMPK, and Akt may hold a central role in the pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease (AD), although the precise mechanisms involved remain unclear.

The present study aimed to investigate the impact of OS on cellular antioxidant defence mechanisms and tau phosphorylation over time. Specifically, the study sought to elucidate the underlying mechanisms linking OS to these

alterations and tau pathology, with a particular focus on the activation of the LKB1, AMPK, and Akt signalling axis under conditions of OS.

Methods

SH-SY5Y culture and differentiation

The cultivation and differentiation of human neuroblastoma cells were conducted following a previously established protocol [25]. In brief, SH-SY5Y cells were cultured in T75 flasks (Sarstedt, Australia) using complete media consisting of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM), F12 (1:1), 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), and 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ penicillin/100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin. The flasks were then placed in an incubator set at 37°C, with a controlled atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO₂. To induce neuronal differentiation in SH-SY5Y cells, the complete media was replaced with FBS-free medium supplemented with 10 μM all-trans-retinoic acid (RA) and maintained for a duration of 7 days.

Determination of the nontoxic dose of H₂O₂

The induction of oxidative stress (OS) in vitro can be achieved through the treatment of cells with H₂O₂ [26]. As the extent of H₂O₂-derived oxidative stress and its toxic effects may vary across different cell types, we specifically investigated its impact on the viability of differentiated neurons derived from SH-SY5Y cells in the context of our experiments.

To determine the non-toxic concentration of H₂O₂ suitable for our study, a series of dilutions of H₂O₂ were prepared, as outlined in Table 1. The cells were cultured in 96-well plates at a density of 20,000 cells per well and exposed to various concentrations of H₂O₂ (as specified in Table 1) for different durations of either 24 hours, 48 hours, or 5 days. Subsequently, the viability of the cells was assessed using the MTT assay. On the appropriate day, 20 μL of MTT solution (containing 10 mg thiazolyl blue tetrazolium bromide in 2 mL TBS) was added to

Volume of H ₂ O ₂ (μL)	Volume of complete media (DMEM F12 1:1, 10% FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin/streptomycin) (mL)	Final concentration of H ₂ O ₂ (μM)
0	1	Control group
0.1	10	1
1.02	5	10
1.02	1	100
2.04	1	200
3.06	1	300
4.08	1	400
5.10	1	500
6.12	1	600
7.14	1	700
8.16	1	800
9.18	1	900
10.20	1	1000

Table 1. Quantities of H₂O₂ and complete media needed to generate H₂O₂ concentrations ranging from 1-1000 μM (0.3%) for assessing cell toxicity via MTT assay.

each well. The plates were then incubated for 4 hours to allow the cells to metabolize MTT and form formazan crystals. After the incubation period, 200 μ L of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added to each well to solubilize the formazan crystals. The absorbance readings were obtained at wavelengths of 520 nm and 620 nm using a microplate reader (Opsys MR; Dynex Technologies, Chantilly, VA, USA). Finally, the percentage of cytotoxicity was calculated by comparing the absorbance values against the respective concentrations of H₂O₂.

Hydrogen peroxide, compound C (CC) and rapamycin treatment

To investigate the impact of H₂O₂ on p-tau, a non-toxic concentration of 200 μ M H₂O₂ was employed. This concentration was selected based on its negligible effect on neuronal survival across all experimental time points (ranging from 24 hours to 5 days). The treatment involving H₂O₂ was carried out both in the presence and absence of 1 μ M CC [27] (an inhibitor of AMPK and Akt) and 5 μ M rapamycin [28] (an inhibitor of mTOR and Akt), as indicated in Table 2. The control groups received an equivalent volume of the respective solvents (DMSO only).

Protein quantification

Following to various treatment durations, the cells were harvested and collected in lysis buffer comprising 5 mM Tris-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM ethylenediaminepentaacetic acid, 0.2% Triton X-100, 1 μ g/ml pepstatin, 1 μ g/ml leupeptin, 1 mM Na₃VO₄, 0.5 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride, and 50 mM NaF. The lysed cells were then subjected to centrifugation at 10,000 \times g for 30 minutes, allowing for the collection of the supernatant. The quantification of total protein content in each sample was performed using an EZQ assay following an approved protocol (BioRad,

Hercules, CA, USA). Cell samples and ovalbumin standards were loaded onto EZQ paper, and subsequent treatment with 100% methanol was carried out. EZQ developing solution was then applied to the paper, enabling the quantification of protein concentrations using Image Lab software.

Western blot analysis

Western blot analysis was conducted by loading 30 μ g of each sample, along with the sample buffer, into the wells of an AnykD™ TGX Stain-free gel. An electric current was applied for 20 minutes at 100V and 300 mA, followed by the transfer of proteins onto a PVDF membrane. After blocking, the membranes were subjected to incubation with primary antibodies, which were procured from Cell Signalling (Australia) and Santa Cruz (USA), targeting the following proteins: p-tau (Ser396) (1:500), p-tau (Ser262) (1:200), tau (1:200), p-AMPK (Thr172) (1:250), AMPK (1:250), p-Akt (Ser473) (1:500), Akt (1:500), p-LKB1 (Ser431) (1:500), LKB1 (1:500), SOD2 (1:2000), p1 (1:1000), p4 (1:1000), catalase (1:500), and β -actin (1:500). The membranes were incubated with HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies, with the following dilutions: anti-mouse (1:3000), anti-rabbit (1:3000), and anti-sheep (1:10,000). ECL developing and chemiluminescence signal detection were performed using a Fuji LAS4000 imager. The obtained images were quantified using Image J molecular imaging software and normalized with respect to β -actin intensities.

Statistical analysis

The data were subjected to analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics software and were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). To assess the differences between the means of various groups, a one-way ANOVA was employed, followed by post hoc Tukey's test. Statistical significance was considered at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Determination of nontoxic concentration of H₂O₂

The assessment of cell cytotoxicity against various concentrations of H₂O₂ was performed utilizing the MTT assay. Differentiated SH-SY5Y cells were exposed to H₂O₂ concentrations ranging from 1 μ M to 1000 μ M for durations of 24 hours, 48 hours (short-term), and 5 days (long-term). The H₂O₂ cytotoxicity-concentration relationship is depicted in Figure 1A (24 h), Figure 1B (48 hours), and Figure 1C (5 days). Notably, H₂O₂ demonstrated no cytotoxicity at concentrations \leq 800 μ M during the initial 24 and 48-hour exposures (Figure 1A, B). However, upon 5 days of H₂O₂ exposure, a significant increase in toxicity was observed at lower concentrations, starting from 500 μ M (One-Way ANOVA, * $p < 0.05$) (Figure 1C). Considering these findings, the safe concentration of 200 μ M was chosen for this study, taking into consideration the immediate neurotoxicity implications.

Effect of H₂O₂ (200 μ M) on p-tau (Ser²⁶²) and p-tau (Ser³⁹⁶) in the presence and absence of compound C (CC) and rapamycin

To investigate the influence of oxidative stress (OS) on tau phosphorylation (p-tau), the levels of p-tau at two residues, Ser262 and Ser396, were evaluated, and their ratio to total tau was calculated. These specific sites, Ser262 and Ser396, represent commonly phosphorylated residues in Alzheimer's disease (AD) and exhibit varying sensitivities to different tau kinases. Ser262 is notably sensitive to adenosine monophosphate protein kinase (AMPK), while Ser396 is primarily affected by glycogen synthase kinase 3 β (GSK3 β) [29].

During the experimental procedure, a consistent OS insult was indicated by the application of a repeated dose of H₂O₂ in one group, whereas the non-changing media condition represented a

Fig. 1 illustrates the relative absorbance of formazan at 520 nm in differentiated SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells following exposure to various concentrations of 0.3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) ranging from 1 to 1000 μ M. The absorbance measurements were taken at three different time points: (A) 24 hours, (B) 48 hours (where H₂O₂ demonstrated non-cytotoxicity at concentrations \leq 800 μ M), and (C) 5 days (with significant toxicity observed at concentrations \geq 500 μ M) (One Way ANOVA, * $p < 0.05$). To ensure accuracy, the absorbance values were corrected by subtracting the background absorbance measured at 620 nm. Error bars depict the SD.

single initial H₂O₂ insult without subsequent additional OS. An initial dephosphorylation of tau at Ser262 was observed (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05), regardless of media change. Extended exposure to OS treatments for 5 days led to increase in tau phosphorylation at Ser262 (Fig. 2A, B) (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05).

Under rapamycin treatment, p-tau at Ser262 remained elevated (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05 vs control), while CC reduced hyperphosphorylation of tau following 5 days of OS (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05 vs control) (Fig. 2A, C).

Fig. 2. Western-blot analysis showed an initial dephosphorylation of p-tau at Ser262 relative to total tau, followed by hyperphosphorylation after 5 days of oxidative stress (OS) (**p* < 0.05). In cells subjected to 5 insults of 200 μM H₂O₂, tau hyperphosphorylation at Ser262 was blocked by 1 μM compound C (CC) (**p* < 0.05), but not after 5 μM rapamycin. The values are expressed as a percentage change relative to control, corrected by β-actin level. Error bars depict the SD.

Fig. 3. Western-blot analysis revealed an initial dephosphorylation of p-tau at Ser396 (One Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05 vs control), followed by a subsequent rephosphorylation at day 5 (***p* < 0.05, day 5 vs day 4). The rephosphorylation did not surpass the levels observed in the control group. 1 μM compound C (CC) and 5 μM rapamycin reduced p-tau at Ser396 (**p* < 0.05). All values presented are expressed as a percentage change relative to the control and were corrected using the β-actin level as a reference. Error bars depict the SD.

Regarding Ser396, tau exhibited a dephosphorylation at 2 to 4 days (significant at day 4, $*p < 0.05$), followed by DAY 5 rephosphorylation ($*p < 0.05$ day5 vs day 4). However, this rephosphorylation did not reach significant levels beyond the control group

(Fig. 3A, B). Overall, treatment with CC and rapamycin effectively reduced p-tau at Ser396 (One-Way ANOVA, $*p < 0.05$) (Fig. 3A, C).

Fig. 4. (A) The Western-blot analysis revealed a notable increase in AMPK activity (p-AMPK (Thr172)/ total AMPK ratio), which was found to be significant in all groups with changing media, and in the non-changing media group after 5 days of OS exposure (One Way ANOVA, $*p < 0.05$). Treatment with 1 μM compound C (CC) and 5 μM rapamycin notably enhanced AMPK activity, particularly after 3 days of H₂O₂ treatment (One Way ANOVA, $*p < 0.05$). All values are expressed as a percentage change relative to the control group and were accurately corrected using the β-actin level as a reference. Error bars depict the SD.

Effect of H₂O₂ (200 μM) on AMPK activity in the presence and absence of compound C (CC) and rapamycin

Previous studies have suggested that AMPK, a pivotal energy regulator during cellular stress, functions as a tau kinase by exerting a specific effect on phosphorylating the Ser²⁶² residue [20; 21].

To investigate the role of AMPK in tau phosphorylation under oxidative stress (OS) conditions, we examined the activation of AMPK (p-AMPK (Thr172)/AMPK ratio) following time-dependent H₂O₂ treatment.

During 2-4 days of OS exposure, when the culture media remained unchanged, AMPK activity remained consistent with the control group. In contrast, when the media was changed with fresh media after the time-dependent OS exposure, AMPK hyperactivity was observed (One-Way ANOVA, $*p < 0.05$). After 5 days of OS, notable AMPK hyperactivity was observed, irrespective of media change (One-Way ANOVA, $*p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4A, B).

Rapamycin and CC did not influence the hyperactivity of AMPK; in fact, AMPK activity was enhanced with exposure to rapamycin and CC (Fig. 4A, C), particularly after 3 days of

H₂O₂ treatment (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05).

Effect of H₂O₂ (200 μM) on LKB1 activity in the presence and absence of compound C (CC) and rapamycin

As the upstream kinase of AMPK, LKB1 plays a critical role in facilitating AMPK phosphorylation at Thr172, leading to its activation [30].

To investigate the impact of oxidative stress (OS) on LKB1 activity, we examined the levels of p-LKB1 in relation to total LKB1 under time-dependent treatment with H₂O₂, both in the presence and absence of exchanged media.

Our findings revealed a significant increase in LKB1 activity under the OS condition (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05). This enhanced activity of LKB1 remained significantly higher than the control group after treating the cells with CC and rapamycin (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05) (Fig. 5).

Effect of H₂O₂ (200 μM) on Akt activity in the presence and absence of compound C (CC) and rapamycin

To elucidate the potential mechanism underlying the inability of Compound C (CC) and rapamycin to inhibit AMPK under oxidative stress (OS), we investigated the activity of Akt, which plays a direct role in inhibiting AMPK [31; 32].

The activity of Akt, as indicated by the ratio of p-Akt at Ser473 to total Akt, showed a progressive increase with the number of H₂O₂ exposures, regardless of whether the media was changed with fresh media or left unchanged (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05) (Fig. 6A, B). However, exposure to CC and rapamycin significantly reduced Akt activity (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05) (Fig. 6A, C), indicating their inhibitory effect on Akt under OS conditions.

Fig. 5. (A) The Western-blot analysis of LKB1 activity (p-LKB1 (Ser431)/total LKB1) demonstrated a progressive increase in LKB1 activity under OS (One Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05). The elevated LKB1 activity remained higher than the control even after treatment with 1 μM compound C (CC) and 5 μM rapamycin (One Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05). All values are presented as a percentage change relative to control and were normalized using the β-actin level as a reference. Error bars depict the SD.

Fig. 6. Western-blot analysis demonstrated a notable increase in Akt activity (p-Akt at Ser473/total Akt) in differentiated SH-SY5Y cells following H₂O₂ treatment, regardless of whether the media was changed or left unchanged (One Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05). Subsequently, the activity of Akt was significantly diminished upon exposure to 1 µM compound C (CC) and 5 µM rapamycin (One Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05). All values are presented as a percentage change relative to the control group and were accurately normalized using the β-actin level as a reference. Error bars depict the SD.

Effect of H₂O₂ (200 µM) on antioxidant enzymes' levels of SOD2, catalase, p1 and p4

The study aimed to examine the effects of exposure to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) at a concentration of 200 µM on the activity of crucial antioxidant enzymes. The enzymes under scrutiny encompassed superoxide dismutase 2 (SOD2), catalase, peroxiredoxin 1 (p1), and peroxiredoxin 4 (p4). Through evaluating the actions of these enzymes, the research sought to gauge the efficacy of antioxidant defence during H₂O₂ exposure, potentially influencing the LKB1/AMPK and Akt signalling pathways, thereby impacting tau phosphorylation.

Superoxide dismutase 2 (SOD2) displayed a progressive augmentation in levels as the frequency of H₂O₂ exposures escalated (One-ANOVA, **p* < 0.05) (Fig. 7A, B, C). In sharp contrast, peroxiredoxin 4 (p4) exhibited a

consistent level akin to the control group across these experimental circumstances (Fig. 7A, H, I). Moreover, both catalase (Fig. 7A, D, E) and peroxiredoxin 1 (p1) demonstrated a decline in response to H₂O₂ exposure, irrespective of the presence or absence of CC (simulating a control condition) and rapamycin (Fig. 7A, F, G) (One-Way ANOVA, **p* < 0.05).

The findings illuminate the intricate responses of these antioxidant enzymes to H₂O₂ exposure, implying a multifaceted regulation of antioxidant defence mechanisms.

The escalating levels of SOD2 suggest an adaptive antioxidant response to combat heightened oxidative stress, while the stable p4 levels indicate a potential steady-state regulation. Conversely, the diminishing levels of catalase and p1 hint at a complex interplay between oxidative stress and regulatory pathways.

Fig. 7. (A) Western-blot analysis showed the increased SOD2 in parallel with the number of exposures to H2O2 (One Way ANOVA, $*p < 0.05$), dose-dependent response. Conversely, both catalase and p1 levels exhibited a decrease (One Way ANOVA, $*p < 0.05$), irrespective of the presence or absence of 1 µM compound C (CC) and 5 µM rapamycin. The level of p4, remained consistent between the OS treated and control groups. All values were expressed as a percentage change relative to control and were accurately normalized using the β -actin level as a reference. Error bars depict the SD.

Discussion

Previous studies, including our own research, have consistently reported elevated levels of oxidative stress (OS) in degenerative neurons of individuals with Alzheimer's disease (AD) [33-35]. In this study, we sought to establish an in vitro model of OS by utilizing pure neuronal cells derived from the human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cell line. Our investigation focused on monitoring changes in phosphorylated tau (p-tau) at two specific residues, Ser262 and Ser396, over a period of up to 5 days of OS exposure.

To ensure the safety and viability of differentiated neurons during the treatment with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), we conducted dose-dependent survival experiments. These experiments allowed us to determine that a concentration of 200 μ M H₂O₂ was appropriate for our study, as it did not immediately compromise cell viability in any of the tested groups. To investigate the impact of oxidative stress (OS) accumulation over time, we implemented different conditions regarding the culture media. While the media was periodically replaced in some experimental groups, it remained unchanged in others.

The discrepancy in media conditions allowed us to simulate the gradual accumulation of OS. The groups in which the media was changed and fresh H₂O₂ was added can be considered as representing a constant and continuous OS insult, while the groups with non-changing media reflect the impact of a single initial OS event without any subsequent exposure to H₂O₂. Furthermore, when treating cells with 200 μ M H₂O₂, we observed an initial decrease in phosphorylated tau (p-tau) at Ser262. However, with prolonged exposure (5 days), we observed an increase in phosphorylation at this site. This observation can be explained by considering that protein phosphorylation is an energy-dependent process [36]. Short-term

exposure to OS may prompt cells to activate adaptive mechanisms, diverting the ATP required for phosphorylation to other essential cellular processes. These processes might include preventing cell death and eliminating H₂O₂ through free radical scavenging, aiming to minimize oxidative damage caused by H₂O₂ exposure [37]. In contrast, continuous OS insult could lead to different outcomes.

In cellular stress conditions, such as oxidative stress (OS), AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) assumes a crucial role in maintaining energy homeostasis [38; 39]. Previous studies have indicated that AMPK exhibits tau kinase activities, particularly at the Ser262 residue [20; 21]. In our investigation, we observed an increase in phosphorylated tau (p-tau) at Ser262 following prolonged exposure to OS, suggesting a potential correlation with AMPK activation. Subsequently, we sought to validate this relationship by examining AMPK activity under OS conditions, which exhibited a parallel increase with the enhanced phosphorylation of tau at Ser262. Similarly, phosphorylation of tau at Ser396 followed a comparable trend, revealing dephosphorylation within the initial four days and gradual rephosphorylation on the fifth day. Nonetheless, this change was not as pronounced as the one observed at Ser262, potentially due to Ser396's higher sensitivity to GSK3 β , a kinase less influenced by OS compared to AMPK.

To substantiate the role of AMPK in tau phosphorylation under OS, particularly at Ser262, we employed an AMPK blocker, compound C (CC), which resulted in reduced p-tau levels. This finding further confirmed the significance of AMPK in the phosphorylation process. Overall, our results, showing the correlation between increased AMPK activity and extended exposure to H₂O₂, align with previous studies that have also demonstrated the impact of OS on AMPK activation [38; 39].

Contrary to our initial expectations, the treatment of cells with CC did not result in decreased AMPK activity. Instead, we observed an unexpected increase in phosphorylated AMPK (p-AMPK) at Thr1172 in response to the CC blocker under OS conditions. This intriguing finding implies the potential concurrent activation of another cellular pathway, namely Akt, given the well-established interaction between Akt and AMPK [40]. Previous reports have highlighted the enhancement of Akt activity under ischemic conditions, manifested by phosphorylation at Ser473, with reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation possibly serving as a link between ischemia and Akt activation [41]. In the present study, we demonstrated a significant and time-dependent increase in phosphorylated Akt (p-Akt) at Ser473 under OS conditions.

Akt activation is known to strongly inhibit AMPK phosphorylation [31; 32] and it is noteworthy that both Akt and AMPK pathways were affected by CC treatment [42; 43]. Our findings indicated a substantial decrease in Akt activation but not AMPK following CC treatment under OS conditions. This suggests that CC treatment inhibited Akt, thereby countering the inhibitory effect of CC on AMPK and resulting in increased AMPK activity and subsequent tau hyperphosphorylation at Ser262, as observed in our study. Hyperactivity of AMPK was similarly observed under rapamycin exposure, providing further evidence for the involvement of the Akt signalling pathway. This aligns with previous studies suggesting rapamycin as an inhibitor of the Akt pathway [44; 45]. Therefore, the inhibitory effect of rapamycin on Akt phosphorylation (Ser473), as seen in our study, may be attributed to removal of inhibition on AMPK (p-AMPK at Thr172), leading to elevated p-AMPK(Thr172)/AMPK

and an additional impact on increasing p-tau (Ser262).

LKB1, the primary upstream kinase of AMPK [30], exhibited a trend like that of AMPK, with a time-dependent increase in activity (elevated p-LKB1/LKB1) under OS conditions. This finding underscores the important role of LKB1 in facilitating AMPK phosphorylation and subsequent activation during cellular stress. Our results not only confirmed this role but also revealed a gradual increase in LKB1 activity as H₂O₂ exposure time increased. Taken together, our findings propose that the combined stimulatory effects (directly and indirectly via LKB1) and inhibitory effects (via Akt activation leading to AMPK inhibition) of OS on AMPK ultimately result in AMPK activation. This suggests that both AMPK and Akt were activated in response to OS, although AMPK activation appeared to be dominant, leading to tau hyperphosphorylation.

Furthermore, our investigation into the levels of antioxidant enzymes in response to oxidative stress (OS) unveiled a higher activity of SOD2 compared to other antioxidant enzymes, namely p1, catalase, and p4. The enhanced activity of SOD2 can be attributed to its role in facilitating the conversion of oxygen radicals to H₂O₂, a reversible reaction that likely occurs during OS conditions within our experimental environment [46]. Our previous studies have demonstrated a significant decrease in SOD2 levels in the brains of individuals with Alzheimer's disease (AD), suggesting a loss of antioxidant defence in degenerative neurons [33; 47]. Interestingly, recent research has indicated that the upregulation of SOD2 in response to OS can sustain AMPK activation [48]. This presents a potential mechanism underlying the observed hyperactivity of AMPK and elevated p-tau in our study.

In contrast, the activity of catalase and p1 was

notably reduced compared to the control group, while p4 activity remained consistent. This observation may be explained by the inhibitory influence of ROS-activated Akt on catalase, as reported previously [49]. This provides additional evidence of Akt's involvement in the neuronal response to OS. Earlier reports have also demonstrated a diminished level of peroxiredoxin 1 and 4 in AD brains [33]. However, the difference in peroxiredoxin 1 and 4 levels observed in our study, despite their identical function in H₂O₂ neutralization, could potentially be attributed to their distinct cellular localization. While p1 is predominantly a cytosolic enzyme, p4 is primarily found in the endoplasmic reticulum [50]. Nonetheless, further investigation is required in future

studies to determine the precise reasons for their differing levels in our OS model.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study sheds light on the impact of time-dependent oxidative stress (OS) on tau hyperphosphorylation, a significant hallmark of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Although initial dephosphorylation of tau was observed, prolonged exposure to OS led to tau hyperphosphorylation, likely as an adaptive response to divert energy towards critical processes during OS. Our findings suggest that extended OS exposure induces activation of Akt, LKB1, and AMPK pathways. The interplay among these three pathways under OS

Fig. 8. Interplay among LKB1, AMPK, and Akt pathways under oxidative stress has been observed. Oxidative stress triggers Akt, LKB1, and AMPK activation. The impact of oxidative stress on AMPK is multifaceted, encompassing both stimulatory and inhibitory components. AMPK can be directly activated by oxidative stress independently of ATP levels. Indirect activation of AMPK occurs by increased LKB1 activity and SOD2 levels, which are elevated in response to oxidative stress. Conversely, the inhibitory effect on AMPK arises from Akt activation, which leads to suppression of AMPK. Akt also exerts a negative influence on catalase and p1, exacerbating oxidative stress conditions. Overall, the interplay between these pathways appears to result in the dominant activation of AMPK, ultimately leading to tau hyperphosphorylation, a hallmark of the observed response to oxidative stress.

eventually results in the predominance of AMPK tau kinase activity, leading to tau hyperphosphorylation. Altered activation patterns of different antioxidant enzymes could both influence and be influenced by these pathways, yielding both negative and positive consequences. A notable example is SOD2, whose activation is deemed essential for cellular protection against OS; however, AMPK activation by this enzyme may contribute to tau phosphorylation, further complicating the pathology of AD (Fig. 8).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.

